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PRAECTICE

POTENTIALS OF AGROECOLOGICAL PRACTICES IN EAST AFRICA WITH A FOCUS ON CIRCULAR WATER-ENERGY-NUTRIENT SYSTEMS

D1.1 – Stakeholder map for Agroecology in East Africa

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Abstract	The mapping of stakeholders involved in Agroecology (AE) aims at identifying existing networks and programmes in AE work while at the same time ascertain their capacity needs as they transit towards AE. This exercise will facilitate an educated selection of relevant stakeholders in the 3 Eastern African countries of Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania in order to select a desirable representative of stakeholders to be actively engaged in the upcoming activities of PraECTiCE project.
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- DMP:** Data management plan
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Agroecology (AE) has evolved from just a study of interaction between agronomy and ecology into a global framework embracing the entire food system from production, distribution and consumption. Progressively, various research, academia, practitioners and other stakeholders have had an emergence of convergent thoughts in AE leading to concurrence in some of the areas around AE. Subsequently, several attempts have been made to quantify the impact of AE in farming practices leading to formation of various international working groups to try and develop AE indicator frameworks. Some of these Decision Supporting Tools (DST) have been tested in some Sub-Saharan countries but none specifically for East Africa despite its unique environmental, socio-economic and political conditions.

This mapping of stakeholders and definition of capacity needs specifically for the three East African countries of Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania strives to embrace the farmers to enable them have a representative voice with the DST and support them in their AE transition by starting with existing frameworks and focusing on practical approaches including provision of a facilitated data collection methodology. Their inclusion is driven by the belief that active engagement of diverse stakeholders in designing of the indicators is required to achieve applicability and reliability of relevant DSTs development process and assessment of outcomes. Besides this, the mapping exercise aimed at identifying key stakeholders in co-creation of networks and learning activities in the project going forward. Finally, the mapping was also aimed at understanding the barriers that hinder accelerated AE transition through identification of capacity needs and how the project can effectively address them.

The mapping exercise was built on a similar activity undertaken in similar projects, more specifically, the Youth in Agroecology and Business Learning Track Africa (YALTA) project implemented in Kenya, Uganda, Rwanda and Ethiopia. With the inclusion of Tanzania, the project aimed to embrace past experience to undertake a credible exercise in the three countries. The mapping also relied heavily on past interaction within the project partners and was complimented by credible publications, online sources, personal interactions and other relevant literature.

The first step involved development of a selection criteria based on specific characteristics that would identify legitimate AE stakeholders. Consequently, this criterion identified 219 stakeholders who were

then targeted for data collection that was administered through an online Google form. Out of this, 141 responses were received for analysis.

The outcome of the mapping process reveals that there are multiple stakeholders within the AE space who are engaged in diverse AE practices and activities. At the core are agricultural producers and producer organizations, research and academia, policy agencies, consumers and consumer groups, development agencies, AE networks, local and international development agencies, multi-lateral organizations including the UN among others. All these play distinct and sometimes complimentary roles in AE from input application, propagation, production, marketing, research, capacity building, extension, policy influencing, certification, accreditation, financing, promotion, processing among others.

The outcome of the analysis revealed that among stakeholders, the most understood concept of AE was in content of sustainable farming practices. This involved production without synthetic applications, soil conservation, biodiversity, circularity, effective land use management, recycling and environmental wellness. Within the content of understanding the holistic elements and principles of AE, this was highest among organizations offering advisory services to producers while diversity was the most understood term describing AE elements. Co-creation of knowledge networks was also top of this understanding hierarchy while governance and solidarity were least understood elements of AE among stakeholders.

Among the principles of AE, soil health was the most applicable concept among stakeholders followed by biodiversity, participation and recycling. The least applicable AE principles were found in livestock/animal production and health where synergy creation, fairness and connectivity could not be traced to their food system.

Among the key challenges faced by producers in their AE transition was inadequate financing and limited support in marketing of their AE produce. Lack of information and data, resistance to change and fear of unknown especially in view of climate change were cited as key obstacles to AE transition. Within researchers and academia, development agencies, low funding for AE programmes coupled with low uptake of AE practices among actors topped the list. For multi-lateral agencies, the unavailability of technical extension services (and budgets) in countries where they operate, weak supply chains especially of AE products as well as low uptake of AE technologies topped their key challenges in accelerated AE transition.

The key capacity development needs among producers were technical extension services while within organizations, skills and functional capacity topped their agenda. The researchers and academia requested for inclusion of AE training in the curriculum and commencement of exchange programmes between local and international universities. For development agencies, capacity building was needed for stakeholders to be able to engage in policy dialogue processes with their local and national governments.

Finally, in view of the merging AE framework, there is need to have a multi-faceted and multi-stakeholders approach that will support the EA farmers to transit to AE. The co-creation of knowledge networks and activities will lead to better sensitization and understanding of AE benefits by stakeholders but more specifically, smallholders in terms of environmental and socio-economic impacts that should be evidently provided and quantified to promote accelerated uptake of AE practices.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AAA	Africa Agribusiness Academy
ABT	Aquabiotech Limited
AE	Agroecology
AFSA	Alliance For Food Sovereignty in Africa
AIF	Agroecological Indicator Framework
CSO	Civil Society Organization
DALF	Department of Agriculture Livestock and Fisheries – Kisumu County
DST	Decision Support Tool
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FBO	Faith Based Organizations
INGO	International Non-Governmental Organization
MAK	Makerere University
MSU	Maseno University
NARO	National Agricultural Research Organization
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
PrAectiCe	Potentials of Agro-ecological practices in East Africa with a focus on Circular Water-Energy-Nutrient Systems
PROTON	Prototipi Limited
RUFORUM	Regional Universities Forum for Capacity Building in Agriculture
SAT	Sustainable Agriculture Tanzania
TAPE	Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation
UGOT	Goeteborgs Universitet

UMU	Uganda Martyrs University
UN	United Nations
VC	Value Chain
YALTA	Youth in Agroecology and Business Learning Track Africa

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE

Agroecology (AE) concept began in 1928 when it was first used to describe the use of ecological methods in the research of commercial plants. Later in the 1930s, it evolved both as a concept and practice and has since appeared in scientific literature. The idea grew in the 1960s, 70s and 80s during which the notion of agro-ecosystem started to transform into an idea of an ecosystem amended by human activity for exploitation purposes.

In the 1990s and 2000s, agroecology has evolved globally from just a study of the interaction between agronomy and ecology, into an agroecological framework embracing the whole food system, defined as a global network of food production, distribution and consumption¹ of food resources and all its components of agricultural, agronomic, economic, social and economic. Over the years there has been numerous research activities globally on the topic, with different organizations and players driving divergent efforts to understand and structure agroecology. In recent years, there has emerged a convergence of thoughts on agroecology by the various research, organizations and stakeholders. The definition, elements and principles of agroecology are just some of the areas that most agroecology players and stakeholders have built consensus on.

There have been several attempts to quantify impacts of sustainable farming practices in general, and AE in particular. Many research activities globally have focused on identifying suitable indicators and estimating socio-economic and environmental impacts. In recent years, several international working groups have been formed to try and develop agroecology indicators, with the most notable ones being FAO - led that feeds into the development of the Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE) and

¹ <https://www.agroecology-pool.org/historical-perspective>

the Groupe de Travail sur les Transitions Agroécologiques (GTAE) that resulted in the Handbook for Evaluation of Agroecology. Other existing frameworks include MESMIS and the Sustainable Intensification Assessment Framework. A handful of tools has emerged, aiming at practically applying the frameworks and supporting the assessment of AE: the Agroecology Criteria Tool (ACT) by Biovision in Switzerland or the SHARP+ by FAO for the AE self-assessment for smallholder farmers are among the most prominent examples.

Despite having these state-of-the-art indicator frameworks and tools, some of which have been tested in Sub-Saharan Africa, none of them are specific to East Africa. Many of the existing approaches target development agencies and policy makers, resulting in a while, very comprehensive, often very theoretical methodology, which is far away from East African farmers' realities. As Kpienbaareh, D. et al.² suggest, threats like climate change, food insecurity and biodiversity loss require evolution of resource governance in decision making that is moving away from a top-down to a bottom-up approach that will enable local communities to have a representative voice in the regulation of the risks they face. It is these gaps that the PrAECTiCe project seeks to address by developing a Decision Support Tool (DST) that will help East African farmers in their AE transition, building on existing frameworks but focusing on practical approaches, including the provision of a facilitated data collection methodology.

The need to get all the stakeholders involved in the development of DST cannot be overemphasized. A meta-analysis (on 119 tools for farm sustainability assessment) published in 2021 comes to the following conclusions; that:

- An active involvement of stakeholders in the designing of indicators is needed to achieve reliable and relevant assessment outcomes
- The indicators themselves should include more complex sustainability framings, covering social themes targeting farmers' characteristics

² Kpienbaareh, D., et al., Spatial and Ecological Farmer Knowledge and Decision-Making about Ecosystem Services and Biodiversity, *Land*, 9 (2020) 356

- Lack of integrating farmers in the assessment framework process is hampering the applicability and usefulness of the AE framework. A recent study of Wiget et al.³ (on 19 different agricultural sustainability assessment tools), states that lack of linkages between farmers in real-world to environments further points out the missing coverage of local conditions in the Global South, where the tradition of record-keeping and technical equipment are missing. For future work, the study calls for simple assessment measures of evaluation of AE performance, that is scientifically sound while providing relevant knowledge and feedback to farmers; integration of commonly used monetary productivity indicators and validation of the framework/tool regarding their impact and applicability

FIGURE 1: THE PRACTICE CONCEPT

³ Wiget, M., Muller, A., Hilbeck, A., 2020, Main challenges and key features of indicator-based agroecological assessment frameworks in the context of international cooperation, Ecology and Society, 25(3) 25

To get the stakeholders meaningfully involved in development of a DST that is useful for them and their context, it is paramount to develop an in-depth understanding of who these stakeholders are, their locations and distribution, the activities and programmes they undertake, the strengths and weaknesses they possess, the challenges they face and their training needs. This was recognized as a requirement by the PrAectiCe project and therefore detailed mapping of stakeholders' was built-in as one of the key and initial components of the entire project.

1.2 PURPOSE OF THE REPORT

The main purpose of agroecology stakeholders mapping is to identify key stakeholders in Kenya, Tanzania and Uganda. The report intends to inform other project activities on which stakeholders' need to be involved in the DST development process, and other co-creation and learning activities. It classifies the stakeholders from each of the countries, highlights their key activities and programmes, and analyzes their capacity needs, with recommendations on how the project can address these needs. The report also highlights why the stakeholders mapping was undertaken, the methodology used and the partners involved.

1.3 SCOPE AND METHODOLOGY

The mapping of stakeholders was building up on a similar exercise undertaken by Africa Agribusiness Academy (AAA) in Kenya, Uganda, Rwanda and Ethiopia in 2019 under the Youth in Agroecology and Business Learning Track Africa (YALTA) project. The focus of this activity was therefore to refine and update the existing database of the stakeholder in Kenya and Uganda, and expand the mapping to other Eastern Africa countries, particularly Tanzania. The mapping was led by AAA, with RUFORUM, AFSA, SAT, MSU, PROTON, ABT, UGOT, DALF, NARO, UMU and MAK participating as task partners.

The overall objective of the mapping was to gain a deeper understanding of the current agroecology context in Eastern Africa to facilitate accelerated transition to agroecology. The stakeholder mapping exercise aimed to achieve the following specific objectives:

- i. Profile stakeholders engaged in agroecology in Eastern Africa by stakeholder category, programmes and activities.
- ii. Profile networks, numbers, and intensity of interactions among agroecology stakeholders in Eastern Africa, and
- iii. Profile capacities, constraints, and opportunities for different stakeholder categories in order to accelerate transition to agroecology in Eastern Africa

The initial task for partners was to develop a criterion of characteristics that would be considered in the identification of the agroecology stakeholders. These characteristics formed the minimum consideration to be met before being considered as a legitimate agroecology stakeholder, and subsequently profiled.

TABLE 1: STAKEHOLDERS IDENTIFICATION CRITERION

Type/ Category	Contribution	Legitimacy	Scale
Value chain actor/ AE practitioner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actively involved along the value chain Has distinct AE practices – different from normal practices in their locality/ activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AE practices already in place 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Significant scale in AE practice to influence the core outcome
Farmers including fish farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actively involved in agri-production Applying at least one agroecology practice in production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AE practices already in place 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AE practice of significant scale to influence the production system
Financier	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offering financial services to AE stakeholders Has specific product tailor-made for AE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Has products and services in place 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least one AE product active in the market
Researcher	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Doing or have done research specific to AE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific research Published papers or abstracts on the research work 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least one research paper/abstract

Type/ Category	Contribution	Legitimacy	Scale
Academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training institutions offering training on AE Practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Has a recognized and certifiable course on AE • Course recognized by relevant certification body 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offering at least a certificate in AE studies
Think Tank/ Expert	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generating knowledge on AE practices • Translating and packaging knowledge for consumption by AE practitioners and the public at large 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have publications, modules, online network, manuals, papers and tools specifically on AE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least one set of AE module, publication and knowledge network
Extension service provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offering extension services on AE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognized extension SP • Has undergone training on AE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working with at least 500 value chain actors
Development Agencies - NGOs, CBOS, FBOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoter / Supporter/ Facilitator • Running programmes focusing on promoting AE practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Has legitimate legal statutes. • Has active programmes on AE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have existed and run AE programmes for at least 1year
Technology providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Producers and marketers of AE specific products and services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Has a specific product or service that is at the center of AE practice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Has at least one product/service in the market

The stakeholders' mapping relied heavily on previous interaction with the project partners and it relied on both secondary and primary data sources. The stakeholder list from partners and mapping report by AAA formed a critical source of secondary data, complemented by publications, online sources and other relevant literature from the project partners and other credible sources. Primary data was obtained from meetings and discussions with the project partners, online data collection sheet and electronic questionnaires administered via Google Forms. Follow up with organizations was done through phone calls, actual visits and emails.

The activity relied on snowball sampling technique that identified stakeholders for questionnaire administration. Any identified stakeholder who met the set criteria was targeted with the questionnaire, meaning there were no limitations on the population and sample size in this exercise.

A total of 219 stakeholders were identified under the entire mapping exercise.

1.4 REPORT STRUCTURE

This report is structured into four main chapters, with chapter one introducing the report and the mapping exercise, elaborating the scope and the methodology used. Chapter two discusses the role of stakeholders in agroecology, defining agroecology as used in the project and the important roles of the stakeholders, with justification of why the mapping was necessary. Chapter three elaborates the different stakeholders that were mapped at different levels and countries while chapter four examines the challenges, capacities and needs of the stakeholders in agroecology transition.

2 ROLE OF STAKEHOLDERS IN AGROECOLOGY AND SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE IN EAST AFRICA

2.1 AGROECOLOGY, ELEMENTS AND PRINCIPLES

The PrAectiCe project defines agroecology:

"Agroecology means productive, sustainable, resilient, and environmentally safe farming and food systems, combining indigenous knowledge with cutting-edge science, optimizing interactions between plants, animals, humans, and the environment, and promoting the transition to fair, just, and sovereign food systems."

PrAectiCe also adopts the 10 elements and 13 principles of agroecology. The mapping exercise also sought to understand how each stakeholder applied these 10 elements and the application of the principles.

FIGURE 2: THE AGROECOLOGY ELEMENTS AS DEFINED BY BARRIOS ET AL 2020 (FAO)

FIGURE 3: PRINCIPLES OF AGROECOLOGY⁴

2.2 ROLE OF STAKEHOLDERS IN PRACTICE

Two important outputs are anticipated to be developed under the PrAectiCe project; an Agroecological Indicator Framework (AIF) that covers integrated aqua-agriculture, and a Decision Support Tool (DST) for identifying best agroecological practices. These tools must be relevant and adapted to the agroecological

⁴ <https://www.agroecology-europe.org/the-13-principles-of-agroecology/>

context of Eastern Africa. For the AIF and DST to be relevant, they must be designed to be relevant to the current and future agroecology context in Eastern Africa. No other stakeholders are best suited to provide the current agroecology context in Eastern Africa other than those who are currently engaged in it. Given that the focus of the PrAectiCe project is to facilitate wider scale transition of Eastern Africa to agroecology, smallholder farmers and agroecology advisors were critical in providing the current context in Eastern Africa.

In order to develop an AIF and DST that are relevant to the actors within the East African Agro-Ecology Sphere, it was crucial to involve these actors strongly in the mapping and development of an AE framework. This means that co-creation process with a wide range of stakeholders along the whole project timeline being at the core of the Research and Innovation Action. Putting the needs of the East African smallholder farmer at the centre, the engagement process also involves AE advisors that will use the PrAectiCe DST, as well as, amongst others, policy makers, researchers, agripreneurs and advocacy groups. The engagement programme is developed in a way to ensure that activities are tailored to the needs and requirements of each stakeholder group to yield the best outcome possible. Stakeholders' involvement is designed not only to provide input to the research activities but to also provide the opportunity for them to validate the developed conclusions and results.

This multi-stakeholder engagement programme starts with a mapping of all the key stakeholders in the East African ecosystem. This was designed to ensure that the project identifies and includes representatives from all key stakeholders in the co-creation and other upcoming activities including further research and designing of best practices. the research action and the outcomes are therefore inclusive of their input, fitted to their needs and applicable to their contexts.

3 IDENTIFICATION OF KEY STAKEHOLDER GROUPS AND ROLES IN EAST AFRICA

East Africa region, Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania in particular, has a rich diversity of agroecology stakeholders. The mapping exercise isolated key categories of agroecology stakeholders as follows:

- i. **Producers and Producers Organizations:** This category includes small-scale farmers, family farmers, agroecological practitioners, and agricultural producers who apply agroecological principles and practices on their farms and their organizations. They are directly involved in the production of food and other agricultural products using sustainable and ecologically sound methods.
- ii. **Consumers and Food Movements:** Consumers play a crucial role in agroecology as they have the power to influence demand for agroecological products. They are concerned about food quality, safety, and the environmental impact of their choices. Food movements and consumer organizations advocate for agroecological practices, promote local and organic food, and encourage sustainable consumption patterns.
- iii. **Researchers and Academia:** Researchers, scientists, and academic institutions contribute to the development and advancement of agroecological knowledge, principles, and techniques. They conduct studies, experiments, and research to understand ecological processes, promote biodiversity, enhance soil health, and improve farming systems.
- iv. **Policy Makers and Government Agencies:** Government entities and policymakers play a crucial role in shaping agricultural policies, regulations, and incentives that can either support or hinder agroecology. They can provide financial support, create favourable policy frameworks, and establish regulations that promote agroecological practices.
- v. **Local/National Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and Civil Society:** NGOs and grassroots organizations are often actively involved in promoting agroecology at the local levels. They work to raise awareness, provide training and technical support to farmers, facilitate knowledge exchange, and advocate for policies that prioritize sustainable and equitable agricultural systems.

- vi. International NGOs: International NGOs are actively involved in promoting agroecology both at the local and regional/global levels. They work to raise awareness, provide training and technical support to farmers, facilitate knowledge exchange, fund research and adoption actions, and advocate for policies that prioritize sustainable and equitable agricultural systems. Their geographical scope of operations goes beyond the borders of a single country.
- vii. United Nations Agencies and Multi-Lateral Organizations: Some UN agencies and multilateral organizations have been instrumental in the development of agroecology in the region. Their work in the region has been mostly centered around research, policy development, cross-learning support, awareness creation and funding towards adoption of agroecology practices.
- viii. Networks: These bring more than one organization engaged in agroecology work for collective actions, experience sharing and cross-learning. Their coverage be national or cross border in nature.
- ix. Agribusiness and Industry: Agribusinesses and companies involved in agriculture and food production can have a significant impact on agroecology. Some companies are adopting agroecological approaches in their operations, while others may require persuasion or regulation to align their practices with sustainable principles.

3.1 AGROECOLOGY STAKEHOLDERS IDENTIFIED IN THE MAPPING EXERCISE

3.1.1 UN Agencies, Multilateral Organizations, International NGOs, and Cross-Border Networks

Across the 3 EA countries, several cross-border organizations were identified as key agroecology stakeholders playing key support roles in agroecology research, awareness creation and capacity building. They were also involved in knowledge management and cross-learning, policy development support and funding of agroecological practices in some instances. The identified organizations in this category included:

TABLE 2: INTERNATIONAL AND REGIONAL STAKEHOLDERS

Organization's Name	Category	Contact	Description
African Organic Agriculture Network (AfrONet)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://eoai-africa.org/	To develop a unique organic agriculture sector based on the principles of ecology, health, fairness and care to guarantee food security, food sovereignty and sustainable development.
Agha Khan University	Academia	https://www.aku.edu/ieda/Pages/home.aspx	AKU is one of the leading centers in East Africa for providing diverse programmes designed for the professional development of educators and educational researchers with our cutting edge and regionally relevant research and leading academic staff, they work to improve the quality of education in East Africa by offering graduate degrees in education as full-time and part-time; tailored professional development courses; educational interventions and influence educational policies by working with communities and other stakeholders.
Food and Agricultural Organisation of the United Nations (FAO)	UN Agency	https://www.fao.org/about/about-fao/en/	FAO's goal is to achieve food security for all and make sure that people have regular access to enough high-quality food to lead active, healthy lives. With 195 members - 194 countries and the European Union, FAO works in over 130 countries worldwide.
International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA)	Research Organization	https://www.iita.org/	Africa Research In Sustainable Intensification for Next Generation (Africa RISING)
Participatory Ecological Land Use Management (PELUM) Kenya	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.pelumkenya.net	The Association works to improve the livelihoods of small-scale farmers and the sustainability of farming communities, by fostering ecological land use management.
World Vision	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.wvi.org/	We implement sustainable development projects in education, health, child protection, food security, economic empowerment, as well as Water, Sanitation and Hygiene
ACORD International	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.acordinternational.org	Undertake trainings in Applied Agroecology, Bio intensive Kitchen garden and food forests for project teams to ensure knowledge transfer to beneficiaries.

3.1.2 National/Local Stakeholder - Kenya.

TABLE 3: LOCAL/NATIONAL STAKEHOLDERS - KENYA

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
African Biodiversity Network	Farmers Organization	https://africanbiodiversity.org/about-us-2/	ABN's mission is to ignite and nurture a growing African network of individuals and organizations working passionately from global to local level, with capacity to resist harmful developments and to influence and implement policies and practices that promote recognition and respect for people and nature.
Agribusiness Solutions Ltd	Farmers Organization	https://agribizzsolutionsltd.wordpress.com/about-us/	Agribusiness solutions started as a consultancy firm, which specialized in agribusiness financial literacy training and market linkages. However, with time it got other assignments such as aggregate sorghum and millet by EA Breweries. Currently, they are working with farmers in aggregation, and pre and post-harvest support.
Agrinutrition	Farmers Organization		Agrinutrition are involved in the moringa and sunflower value chains.
Aquaculture Barn Limited	Farmers Organization	https://www.google.com/search?q=aquaculture+barn+limited&oq=Aquaculture+Barn+Limited&gs_lcrp=	Integrated agri-aquaculture with production of fish fingerlings and crops under circular production system.
Badilisha Community Permaculture Center	Research Organization	https://badilisha.org/	Promoting permaculture design and ethics on Lake Victoria
BIGRAC(Best in God Regenerative Agroecology Centre)	Others		BIGRAC does Community advocacy on i.e. pollinator protection, ASAL system management, nutrition, value addition, healthy sanitation, holistic gender bases violence and kids, youths, women, people with disabilities inclusivity. Secondly, Soil and water conservation, Agroecological Regenerative shamba practices i.e. Regenerative agriculture, organic agriculture and permaculture, and Smart nurseries for afforestation, reforestation and pollinator protection e.g. Moringa, bamboo, acacia, aloe and seeded fruit trees for perennial.
Biovision Africa Trust	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://biovisionafricatrust.org/	Biovision Africa Trust (BvAT) is a not-for-profit organization established in Kenya in 2009 by the Biovision Foundation for ecological development in Switzerland and supported by the International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology (ICIPE) in Nairobi. The Trust's goal is to alleviate poverty and improve the livelihoods of smallholder farmers in Kenya and other

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
			African countries through supporting dissemination of information and knowledge on appropriate technology to improve human, animal, plant, and environmental health.
Bukura Agricultural Training College	Academia		It is one of the oldest agricultural training institution based in Kenya and conducts training and research on diverse agricultural and agribusiness fields including AE.
Bungoma County Youth Forum	Farmers Organization	https://www.facebook.com/groups/856405214404130/	Food waste management, Agroforestry, cover cropping, nutrient management.
Bungoma County Youth in Agribusiness Organization	Farmers Organization	https://www.facebook.com/p/Bungoma-county-youth-agribusiness-100079202302822/?paipv=0&eav=Afbb0aCIU1mhGxjgXGLQnhSG7ANNwZOdjIWCYsDjeZjNepxXrhziVH2r4CqGMOakyl8&_rdr	Sensitizes youths in Bungoma County on the importance of sustainable farming.
Bungoma County Youth Visionary Network	Farmers Organization	https://nourishingafrica.com/index.php/entrepreneurs/paul-wabomba-42782	Food waste management, Agroforestry, cover cropping, nutrient management.
Camlpo Limited	Farmers Organization	https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/12861073	Revolutionizing Agriculture, Empowering Farmers, Nurturing Sustainability, Driving a Green Future with Precision Farming and Agri-tech
Cereal Growers Association (CGA)	Farmers Organization	https://cga.co.ke/	Its main purpose is to bring together commercial cereal farmers to promote collective action for the sustained improvement of their farming enterprises and in addressing industry challenges in Kenya.
Community Research in Environment and Development Initiatives (CREADIS)	Farmers Organization	https://creadiskkenya.org/	Integrated Farming/ISFPM/CA/Agroforestry
Connie's Farm Enterprise	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)		Organic Farming and involved in production and packaging.

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
Continental Produce Ltd	Fresh Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://www.kenyatradeportal.go.ke/content/continental-fresh-produce-ltd	Livestock and crop production.
Dudu Masters	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://dudumasters.com/	Trainings on Insect farming i.e. Black Soldier Fly farming and Red Worms Farming. Provision of organic fertilizer made from the worms
Eastern African Farmers Federation (EAFF)	Farmers Organization	https://www.eaffu.org/	Enhancement of food security, food sovereignty, and poverty alleviation through Regional farmer empowerment through lobbying and advocacy for pro-poor policies.
Farmers Choice	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://farmerschoice.co.ke/	Rearing of black soldier flies
FIPS-Africa	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://fipsafrica.org/home/	FIPS Africa is involved in What Works Where and for Whom (4Ws) project funded by the McKnight Foundation's Global Collaboration for Resilient Food Systems Kenya Crop and Dairy Market Systems (KCDMS) funded by USAID Mission Grow, funded by US-based Foundation International Training and Coaching of other organisations
Frelin Fresh Limited	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://vc4a.com/ventures/frelin-fresh-limited/	Promoting planting of avocado which is a tree commercial crop, offering good agricultural practices
GFA Consulting group	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://www.gfa-group.de/	Vermi-composting/Legumes/Value Addition
Gods Way	Others		Urban Permaculture
Goshen Farm Exporters Ltd	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://www.goshen.co.ke/	Organic food production, Agrircircularity
Green Foundation	Africa NGO/CSO/FBO	http://www.greenafricafoundation.org/	Green Africa Foundation was founded in Kenya in 2000 with a focus of implementing practical hands-on community driven projects aimed at greening the African continent.

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
Green Farm Solutions	NGO/CSO/FBO		Green farm Solutions is a project focusing on reforestation and environmental conservation in Nakuru County. The project aligns with broader environmental and agroecological goals, including the Greenfarm School Program, which promotes tree planting and environmental conservation in schools. The “Adapt-a-Agroforest” Program supports reforestation activities in cut-down forests, integrating trees into agricultural systems for sustainability. The Greenfarm Kitchen Gardens program empowers rural farmers with knowledge about agroecological practices, promoting sustainable farming methods. The project's main goal is to increase forest cover, raise awareness about reforestation, and educate communities about the importance of trees and environmental conservation. However, the project primarily focuses on tree planting and reforestation. More details on agroecological practices would be helpful.
Healthy Harvest Enterprise	Farmers Organization		Sustainable farming, recycling, production of organic products, farmer empowerment, creation of green manures, and crop diversification.
Kakamega County Youth in Agribusiness Association	Farmers Organization	https://www.facebook.com/p/Kakamega-Youth-Agripreneurs-Kcyaa-100063781321517/	Promoting youths in Kakamega to venture into agribusiness.
KALRO Kakamega	Research Organization	https://www.kalro.org/kai net/node/225412	Soil testing, Mixed cropping
Kamumo Products Ltd	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)		Fruit processing
Kenya Institute of Organic Farming (KIOF)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.kiof.net/	Exists solely for the benefit of the public at large by promoting rural development and education in organic agriculture and related marketing services.
Kenya Livestock Producers Association	Farmers Organization	http://www.klpakenya.org	We believe that lasting impact happens when every link with the different agricultural value chains are strengthened. We partner with all the key agricultural players to strengthen farmer-to-fork agricultural systems. We create linkages to public-private partnerships to facilitate trade and value chain growth.

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
Kenya National Farmers' Federation (KENAFF)	Farmers Organization	www.kenaff.org	Represents the interests of farm families as the legitimate farmers' voice with the objective of articulating issues affecting them through focused lobby and advocacy, targeted capacity building and promotion of sector stakeholders' cohesiveness in dispensing progressive uptake of agricultural innovations for enhanced socio-economic status of the farmers
Kenya Organic Agriculture Network - KOAN	Farmers Organization	https://www.koan.co.ke/	KOAN is membership organization with members across the country and unites producers, exporters, traders, NGOs and likeminded individuals and organizations in promoting Organic Agriculture in Kenya. The organization represents over 200,000 farmers, exporters and works with partners throughout the country.
Kieru Ltd	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://kierufoods.co.ke/	Agro processing
Kimaeti Farmers Association	Farmers Organization	https://www.kimaetifarmerscbo.org/	Bananas/Value addition/Trainings/Agroforestry
Kisumeo Organics	Multilateral Agency	https://www.facebook.com/confettieventss/	Circular aquaculture
Kuuno Agribusiness Ltd	Farmers Organization	https://ke.linkedin.com/in/wambui-jane-wairimu-8bb46892	circular economy
Lacamo Digital Organics	NGO/CSO/FBO		Organic Farming/Apiculture/Legumes/Agroforestry
Mabanga ATC	Research Organization	https://airc.go.ke/directory/mabanga-ftc/	Crops/Animals/ISFM/Trainings/
Magos Farm Enterprises Ltd	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)		Provision of farm input and construction of climate smart structure
Meru Horticulture Ez Ltd.	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://www.merugreens.com/	Production of different crops according to their genetic demands on agroecology.

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
Meru Organics	Farmers Organization	https://www.facebook.com/Meru-Organics-500690379995508/	*Sustainable farming practices *Crop diversification *Soil health improvement *Community education *Advocacy
Momul Agroforestry Group Ltd.	Others	https://www.f6s.com/momulagroforestrygroupLtd	Propagation of various plants seedlings
Nyangorora Processors Company	Banana Limited Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://vc4a.com/ventures/nyangorora-banana-processors-limited-company/	Banana value chain
Real IPM	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://realipm.com/about-us/	produce high quality predatory mites and Bio pesticides based on living organisms.
Refugee and Host Resilience Initiative" REHORI"	Governments Department/Agency/Programme	https://www.rehori.org/	We do stand with community special refugee and some host to boost and sustain their living and resilient, through permaculture ecosystems design for most at risk in GBV context and indigenous people to access local resources.
Sam's Fruit trees farm.	Farmer		Soil health, Biodiversity, Efficiency, Recycling.
Sang'alo Technical Institute	Academia	https://sist.ac.ke/	Biogas, Crops, Livestock
Shambabest	Farmers Organization	https://www.studocu.com/row/document/mount-kenya-university/bachelors-of-science-in-information-technology/shambas-best-business-plan-2023/62805407	Production of horticultural crops and value addition.
Shibuye Fish Farmers Group	Farmers Organization		aquaculture farmers coming together to form an organization for promotion of sustainable farming.
Siaya County Youth Forum- Agribusiness Forum	Farmers Organization	https://www.facebook.com/groups/1518176305101593/	This is a group bringing together youths and young scholars from Siaya county to come up with political and developmental vision for the county.
Super Gibs Coffee Ltd	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	http://supergibs.com/	on our coffee farming, we grow coffee geared towards organic farming /inter cropping with macadamia for shade growing, growing vetiver grass for soil erosion and mulching and using organic fertilizer
Sustainable Agriculture and Community	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://sacdepkenya.org/	Working with resource-limited and marginalized communities to sustainably utilize locally available

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
Development Programmes (SACDEP)			resources for livelihood improvement through sustainable ecological agriculture
Sustainable Mobilization of Agricultural Resource Technologies	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.koan.co.ke/smart-initiative/	a community based not-for profit organization working in West Pokot and Trans-Nzoia Counties promoting ecological organic agriculture.
Tembea Youth Group	NGO/CSO/FBO		Integrated Farming/Trainings/Agroforestry/ISFM
The African Conservation Tillage Network (ACT)		www.act-africa.org	The African Conservation Tillage Network (ACT) is a pan-African not-for-profit organization whose membership is voluntary and aims at bringing together stakeholders and players who are dedicated to improving agricultural productivity through sustainable utilization of natural resources of land and water in Africa's farming systems and committed to the principal of mutual collaboration, partnership and sharing of information / knowledge on sustainable natural resources management and drawing on synergies and complementarities.
Tush Poultry Farm	Farmers Organization	https://www.facebook.com/tushpoultry/	Agroecology Workshops, Biodiversity Enhancement, Sustainable Poultry Farming, Rotation and Diversification, Local Farmer Support, Community Engagement, Research and Innovation-
Umoja Sustainable Organic Farming Initiative	Farmers Organization	http://www.umojaafricafund.Org/	We train and mentor small scale farmers on dry land farming, water conservation and marketing of farm produce.
University of Embu	Academia	https://embuni.ac.ke/	Organic farming
Webuye West Agribusiness Youth Group	Farmers Organization	https://www.facebook.com/groups/1543739386014927/	Promoting youths in Kakamega to venture into agribusiness.
Weyama S.H.G	Others		Legumes, Vegetables, Agroforestry, Value addition, and Vermiculture
Yalta - Victor Langat	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)		Value addition of milk to mursik & agro forestry
Young poultry farmers Association	Farmers Organization	https://www.facebook.com/kepofa/	Poultry rearing. Cultivation of indigenous cash crops, such as tomatoes, onions, maize and black beans.

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
Youth Empowerment for Peace Organisation	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://youth-empowerment-for-peace-organization.business.site/?utm_source=gmb&utm_medium=referral	Use of organic materials, BSF and recycling

3.1.3 National/Local Stakeholder - Tanzania

TABLE 4: LOCAL/NATIONAL STAKEHOLDERS - TANZANIA

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
Action Aid Tanzania	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://tanzania.actionaid.org/land-and-climate	building resilience capacity of people and advocate for equal treatment between men and women for fair redistribution of productive resources such as land, farm inputs and access to financial services. We Advocate for increased budget allocation in support of Agro ecological interventions and public financing to agriculture. We also promote Climate Resilient Sustainable Agriculture as means of strengthening food systems and the capacity of smallholder farmers to adopt climate changes. Food sovereignty and agro-ecological adaptation and Promoting land rights for enhanced resilience of livelihoods
Actions for Development Programmes ADP-Mbozi	NGO/CSO/FBO	http://www.adpmbozi.or.tz	organic and/or ecological farming initiatives, based on EOA practices and principles
Agribusiness Usambara	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://tupandeusambara.wordpress.com/	Agribusiness Usambara main aim is promoting sustainable local development and strengthening communities in order to improve the living conditions and quality of life for all people living in the area of Lushoto District
Agriculture Development and Community Health (ADEACH)	NGO/CSO/FBO		Educating Farmers and community on Planting cover crops, water and waste management, managing grazing, permaculture, polyculture farming, integrated pest managements, recycling, use of improved seeds, sand
Agriiversity Tanzania	Farmers Organization	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61550579606270&locale=hi_IN&page=0&eav=AfbOgToLApna6zkvrOEsjina0DWy9HWGB	Promoting sustainable agricultural practices like use of compost and soil management practices like mulching, promoting beekeeping projects to members,

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
		LYuX9ep2uP09sAjnfcvwBaZ BKyh5w4Rck	encourage use of local technology like use local crops storage.
Alliance Ginneries Limited	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://www.allianceginneriesltd.com/contact	Alliance Ginneries does organic cotton production-produce maize, sun flower in Tanzania, Zambia and Zimbabwe.
Aman Cashewnut Enterprise	Farmers Organization	https://vc4a.com/ventures/amani-cashewnut-enterprises/	Aman Cashew nuts is a group of young farmers who do cashew production and processing
Asili Agribusiness Company Ltd	Farmers Organization	https://asili.ag/	Asili Agribusiness aim is to catalyze a more equitable, resilient and regenerative food system and to transform agriculture into the flourishing industry it ought to be.
Bio sustain Company Limited	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	http://www.biosustain.de/	Aim to revive cotton production using organic farming and to provide markets for organic certified products - with an emphasis on high quality oriented production in Singida Region and now extended to Simiyu and Tabora Regions in Tanzania
Biotan Group Ltd	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	http://www.biotan.at/abolut-us/	Deals with cashew nuts production and finding ways of increasing production in Tanzania.
chema programme	NGO/CSO/FBO	http://chematanzania.org/	Training farmer on climate smart agriculture- on sustainable agriculture carry policy dialogue at different levels on climate mater agriculture and resilience fishing farming-two fish ponds on the farmer distribution of indigenous seeds to farmer use of energy saving stove briquette production- charcoal with less use of carbon monoxide beekeeping and honey production tree planting and environmental conservation.
Community Development Trust fund (CDTF)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://eaphilanthropy.net/work.org/eapn_members/community-development-trust-fund-cdtf/	Apiculture and to support greenhouses
Control Union	Others	https://tz.linkedin.com/in/control-union-tanzania-30b936193	Provide auditing services.

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
COPE(Cooperazione paesi emergenti)	NGO/CSO/FBO		Water conservation and agricultural training to smallholder farmers
Dada Wadogo	Others	https://www.instagram.com/dadawadogo/?hl=en	Vegetable production, fruits and livestock keeping, poultry.
Development Organization Community Habitat Environmental Management	UN Agency	http://chematanzania.org/	Afforestation, Natural forests regeneration, Promotion of beekeeping and Develop and use of energy saving stoves
Dondwe Farm Enterprise	Farmers Organization	https://www.restova.co.tz/things-do/dondwe-farm-enterprises	Planting different types of crops in the Farm (Organization such maize, cassava Cowpeas, Pigeon peas etc. Also planting different types trees e.g. fruit trees such mangoes, citrus(Oranges) Coconuts, Guinea chestnuts guava, bananas, passion fruits etc. Also the organisation is engaged with growing different types of vegetables such as green pepper, Okra, Spinach.
ECHO	NGO/CSO/FBO		Forestry, green cover manure, agroforestry, forum
Elven Agri Company	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://elvenagri.co.tz/	We are growers and processors of dried tropical fruits, vegetables, chilies & other spices. Our guarantee of quality extends beyond processing and to crop plantation and harvesting. Our dried fruits and spices do not use anything artificial in the entire supply chain process right from crop plantation to final finished ingredient. We don't just process food, we grow it.
Enabel	Governments Department/Agency/Programme	https://www.enabel.be/country/uganda/	Bevac beekeeping value chain support wezesha binti-deals with education and entrepreneurship of girls and youth waskirp-water and sanitation kigoma
Farm Radio International	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://farmradio.org/	Radio programmes for creating awareness
Flora and Fauna Restoration System in Tanzania (FLORESTA)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.fauna-flora.org/countries/tanzania/	Training on agroecological technology , nutrition, agribusiness, value addition and post-harvest handling
Foundation for organic Agriculture Tanzania	Farmers Organization	https://foatz.bio/	Provide knowledge and service to youth and small farmers especially marginalized farmers who have inadequate knowledge of ecological organic farming techniques, market skills and natural/organic products and sustainable live holds
Frank Horticultural and Timber Crops Company LTD (FHTC)	Farmer	https://frankhtc.wordpress.com/	Frank Horticulture main crops include avocados, potatoes, honey which are sold to Domestic market.

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
			Our intention is to sell to the European health food markets and other global international markets.
Ministry of Agriculture	Governments Department/Agency/Programme	https://www.kilimo.go.tz/	Provide education to local farmers on how to increase yields, such as agro forestry, correct spacing generally good agricultural practices so as to improve living standard of people while conserving the environment.
Green Cert Company	Others	https://www.greencert.co.tz/	Certification and delivering training to farmers and other agricultural stakeholders
Guavay Company Ltd	Others	https://we4f.org/innovators/guavay-company-limited	Training and capacity development.
Hands for Children and Women in Tanzania (HACHAWOTA)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.facebook.com/vochawota/	Delivering training on production of organic vegetables.
HELVETAS Tanzania	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.helvetas.org/en/switzerland	Promote regenerative agriculture, organic farming with rotational crops, agro-forestry, thereby building resilience of rural households towards climate change and ensuring biodiversity.
Highlands Organic Company	Others	https://www.ecohubmap.com/company/business/highlands-organic/10gvj04b	Engage in organic avocado farming, Vegetables and spice production and bee keeping.
Humans Resources Entrepreneurship Development Organization (HUREDO)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.hurredo.org/	Promote beekeeping and environmental conservation.
IAM ORGANIC	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://iam.organic/	Food processing and offer training to smallholder farmers & support organic products business (" <i>I am Organic Shop</i> " concept)
Inades-Formation Tanzania	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.inadesformation.net/en/inades-formation-tanzania/	Organic and/or ecological farming initiatives, based on EOA practices and principles
Island of Peace (IDP)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://open.enabel.be/en/TZA/2125/33/u/maisha-bora-international-partners-islands-of-peace-idp.html	Islands of Peace is responsible for improving sustainable access to adequate water for livestock

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
Jane Goodall Organization	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://janegoodall.org/	We are a global community conservation organization that advances the vision and work of Dr. Jane Goodall. By protecting chimpanzees and inspiring people to conserve the natural world we all share, we improve the lives of people, animals and the environment. Everything is connected—everyone can make a difference.
Jog-Agri-consult and Solution	Others	https://www.facebook.com/jogagri/	Jog agri-consult is a consultancy that deals with farmers to increase their production and scale up agriculture in Tanzania.
Kaderes Peasant Development Public Limited Company	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://fairtradeafrica.net/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/Kaderes-Digital.pdf	promotion of organic and market linkage to the market
Kagera Cooperative Union (KCU)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://kcu.or.tz/	KCU is a voluntary Association of 141 Primary Cooperative Societies representing over 60,000 small farmers of the mainly Rubusta Coffee in Kagera Region in the north west of Tanzania (West of Lake Victoria). Each primary society is owned by about 500 small coffee producers. Kagera Co-operative Union (1990) Ltd therefore has about 70,500 members
Kibaha Agricultural Research Institute	Research Organization	https://www.tari.go.tz/tari-kibaha/about-us	mandate to conduct, promote and coordinate sugarcane research in the country.
Kilimo Hai Tanzania (KIHATA)	Farmers Organization	https://www.kilimohai.org/	organic and/or ecological farming initiatives, based on EOA practices and principles
Kilimo Trust	Farmers Organization	https://www.kilimotrust.org/	A sustained and equitable food and nutrition for smallholder farmers
Kilombero Agricultural Training and Research Institute	Research Organization	https://chaguachuo.com/institution/view/kilombero-agricultural-training-and-research-institute	Training agricultural crop production curriculum to students NTA Level 4,5,and 6 research and farmers training on good agricultural practices
Kitovu Cha Maendeleo Safi (KIMAS)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://mabumbe.com/kb/kitovu-cha-maendeleo-safi-kimas-details-profile-overview-tanzania/	Agriculture production and livestock keeping, Apiculture and fishing under farmers group
Kolping Society of Tanzania	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.kolpingtanzania.or.tz/	value chain project - start from see producer to the trader KOLCALFEIN-from the farmer to the industry

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
KSM Organic Fertilizer	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://tz.linkedin.com/in/ksm-organic-fertilizer-b09794218	Processing of organic fertilizer, production of organic coffee and horticulture
Macjaro Limited	NGO/CSO/FBO	info@macjaro.co.tz	Out grower Exporting agroecological products
Matunda Mema T limited	Farmer	https://www.volza.com/company-profile/matunda-mema-t-ltd-p-o-box-404-karagwe-kagera-region-tanzania-14861672/	an organic produce exporter, demonstrates that small-scale East African farmers can benefit from the growing demand for organic products
Mahashree Agro Processing Tz Ltd	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://tz.linkedin.com/company/mahashreeagro	Transforming East African agriculture potential into world class products
Mahinya College of Sustainable Agriculture	Academia	https://mahinyacollege.altervista.org/	The aim of the center is to be a “center of excellence” for agricultural and livestock acknowledgment, focusing on quality and sustainability. We believe in a future in which young generations are able to recognize territorial resources in order to become the wheel that moves Tanzanian economy for which concern agriculture and livestock.
Marafiki wa Afrika Tanzania (MAT)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://marafikiAfrika.or.tz/	MAT was founded with the intention to partner with communities to develop interventions that improve wellbeing of poor and marginalized communities in Tanzania.
Manyara Organic Farming Initiative (MOFI)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://irp.cdn-website.com/53007095/files/uploaded/Vesa_MOFI_presentation_2022.pdf	TRAINING FARMERS ON ORGANIC FARMING AIMING TO ENHANCE FOOS SECURITY Environmental conservation Climate change adaptation on farming and animal rearing
Masasi Community of Organic Agriculture (MACOA)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://iamorganic.co.tz/farmer-organizations-supported-by-swissaid-tanzania-as-part-of-its-2019-2024-country-programme/	Training to smallholder farmers.
Masasi Women Development Association (MAWODEA)	Farmers Organization	https://maasaiwomentanzania.com/	Vegetables and fruit production
Mighty Society Against Poverty (MSOAPO)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://msoapo.or.tz/	Vegetable and fruit production, seasonal crop production, livestock keeping, fishing, seaweed farming

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
Milele Zanzibar Foundation	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://mzfn.org/	At Milele Zanzibar Foundation (MZFN), delivering quality and holistic programming targeting deep and lasting change is at the core of what drives our mission and quest to accelerate progress. Since our establishment in 2014, we have grown to become a reputable, reliable and respected organization in Zanzibar's development landscape.
Mkombozi Agribusiness Enterprises Ltd.	Farmer	https://www.mael.co.tz/	Agribusiness consultants working with farmers to promote sustainable agriculture.
Msonge Organic Family Farm	Farmers Organization	https://www.msonge.co.tz/about	Msonge Farm is a 15ha, multi-enterprise farm, growing food for our own household use, sale to our local community through Pakacha Delivery Baskets, delivery to tourist hotels, and allowing room for events such as our weekly farm-to-table to spread the success of organic farming.
Mtandao wa Vikundi vya Wakulima na Wafugaji Mkoa wa Kilimanjaro - MVIWAKI	Farmers Organization	http://mviwaki.or.tz/	MVIWAKI usually promotes agroecology through enhancing its members (farmers' groups) to apply the sustainable agricultural land management practices like making compost, crop rotation, agriforestry, integrated pest and diseases management, good agronomic practices and other in their farms while joining local and international advocacy movements intending to promote agroecological practices.
Mtandao wa Vikundi vya Wakulima na Wafugaji wa Mkoa wa Manyara (MVIWAMA)	Farmers Organization	https://mviwama.or.tz/	Forest and Farm Facility Programme (FFF) funded by Food and Agriculture Organization of United Nations (FAO) HUSISHA Programme Funded by International Belgium Organization (TRIAS)
Mtandao wa Vikundi vya Wakulima na Wafugaji Mkoa wa Arusha - MVIWAARUSHA	Farmers Organization	https://www.mviwaarusha.or.tz/	Sensitization and mobilization to adapt agroecology Training farmers on all agroecological elements and practices Advocacy Participate in forums with partners who support agroecology and learning
Mtandao wa Vikundi vya Wakulima Tanzania - MVIWATA	Farmers Organization	https://www.mviwata.or.tz/	Research organization.
Mwaisunga Organic Farm Products			
National Plant Genetic Resources Centre	Farmers Organization	https://www.pgrc.go.ug/	Collection and conservation of local seeds

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
Pyxus Agriculture Tanzania	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://www.pyxusintl.com/	Produces sunflower oil.
Remei Tanzania Limited	Others	https://www.remei-tanzania.com/	Deals with different AE practices including agroforestry and beekeeping. Agroforestry project involves cultivation of trees and beekeeping as well as promotion of smoke less stove that reduces environmental destruction by using less energy stoves.
Riom Investment Ltd	Farmer	https://www.linkedin.com/in/abdul-ruta-42757938/?originalSubdomain=tz	Production of vanilla , avocado Hass fruits for export and avocado oil processing, production of birds eye chill, also dealing with green coffee export of higher grades of both Robusta and Arabica from Tanzania .
RUCODIA	NGO/CSO/FBO	http://rucodia.or.tz/	Forming and strengthening farmer organizations, strengthening input systems (access to improved seeds and fertilizers), facilitating market linkages and post-harvest management. Also supports enhancement of good agronomic and soil fertility management practices & agro-enterprise development.
Same and Mwangi Environment Conservation Advisory Organization (SMECAO)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://smecao.jimdofree.com/#:~:text=Since%201994%20SMECAO%20Fund%20has,improving%20livelihood%20of%20the%20communities.	SMECAO Fund has been working in Same and Mwangi Districts, Kilimanjaro region towards conserving and protecting environment through improving livelihood of the communities.
Shirikisho la asasi la kilimo hai Masasi (SHAKHAM)	Farmers Organization	http://kazibongo.blogspot.com/2016/05/project-officer-shirikisho-la-asasi-za.html?m=1	Shirikisho la Asasi za Kilimo Hai Masasi (SHAKHAM) is a federation of organic farmers' associations in Masasi district. The organization mission is to reduce poverty among cashew producers through improved sustainable production and skilled marketing of ecologically produced cashew nut. It was established in November 2014 with a total of 2005 members organized in 25 member associations and is a follow-up of the previous partner MHQFP.
SMAM-SJS Organic Farm	Farmers Organization	https://www.sjsorganic.org/index.php/about-us/sma-mission	"One acre Farming in God's Way" – Practices organic animal husbandry & organic horticulture farming.
St. Francis wa Assisi Mkuranga	Others	st.asisfrancis@gmail.com	Agricultural production of cereal and vegetable crops.
Sustainable Agriculture Tanzania (SAT)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://kilimo.org/	Non-profit organization with the mission to collaborate with relevant partners in public and private sector in order to strengthen their capacity in agroecology.

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
Sustainable Beekeeping and Human Development (SuBeHuDe)	Research Organization	www.subehude.or.tz	Provide short-course training in commercial beekeeping, practical permaculture, eco-entrepreneurship, environmental conservation, renewable energy and climate change action. Also engages in biodiversity and natural resource management as well as community capacity building.
SWISSAID Tanzania	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.swissaid.ch/en/countries/tanzania/	NGO supporting smallholder farming families.
Tanzania Alliance for Biodiversity	NGO/CSO/FBO	http://tabio.org/contact-us.html	Tanzania Alliance for Biodiversity is an alliance of civil society and private sector organizations concerned with biodiversity conservation, with an emphasis on agricultural biodiversity for livelihood security and food sovereignty.
Tanzania Organic Agriculture Movement (TOAM)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.kilimohai.org/	Engages in agroecology trainings. It is the umbrella organization that coordinates and promotes the development of organic farming among farmers, distributors and consumers through networking and information distribution.
Tanzania PanAfrican Investors Association (TAPAIA)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCealB1WGCR529PiiACWiKTA	A community of investors who come together to promote agriculture in Tanzania.
Tanzania Zanzibar Organic Producers Ltd (TAZOP)	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://www.tridge.com/marketplace/basic-sellers/tanzania-organic-products-ltd-tazop	Processor, and exporter of spices mainly dealing with cloves, ginger and vanilla.
TANZPRO Green Ltd	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://www.tanzpro.co.tz/	TanzPro Greens Ltd is a company using fair trade practices that specializes in growing of a variety of organic farming grown horticulture products including fresh fruits and vegetables. They grow organic products without using any synthetic/agrochemical inputs which are harmful to human health and the environment. They are actively engaged in facilitating quality and standard compliance of organic products by specializing in high quality control from cultivation, harvesting, sorting, grading, and packaging to final consumers.
TEMNAR Company Ltd.	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://www.facebook.com/p/Temn-ar-company-limited-100072250098742/	Majors in Sunflower value chain.
The Foundation For Organic Agriculture Tanzania	Farmers Organization	https://foatz.bio/	Supporting the ecological organic community through effective and comprehensive training programs that

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
			are developed to support their strategy and the needs of communities practicing organic agriculture.
Trees for the Future	NGO/CSO/FBO		Support forest garden through cultivation of trees for fences & use of composite manure. They also train the usage of organic pesticides.
Tushiriki Organization	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.usaid.gov/sites/default/files/2022-12/Tushiriki_Pamoja_Fact_Sheet.pdf	Tushiriki organization implements many programmes and projects such as organic agriculture farming, education and awareness about organic farming, distribution of organic seeds and seedlings, capacity building in organic farming in diverse value chains. They also link farmers with agriculture input suppliers, markets and support them in networking.
UWAMWIMA	Farmers Organization	http://uwamwima.com/	Promote organic farming practices.
World Vegetable Center	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://avrdc.org/	Collection and conservation of vegetable genetic resources, Research and Development of vegetable varieties, and capacity building.
Young World Feeders	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://fipsafrica.org/home/	“YES’ (Youth Enhancement through Skills) deals with providing agricultural education to the youth.
Zanzibar Fruits and Vegetables Farmers Association (UWAMWIMA)	Farmers Organization	https://uwamwima.wordpress.com/about	Organic farming practices, including agroforestry.

3.1.4 National/Local Stakeholder – Uganda

TABLE 5: LOCAL AND NATIONAL STAKEHOLDERS - UGANDA

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
Advocates Coalition for Development and Environment (ACODE)	Research Organization	https://www.acode-u.org/	Policy think-tank on food and rural development.
Africa 2000 Network	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.a2n.org/ug/	Committed to empowering rural farming communities for sustainable livelihoods in agriculture.

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
AfSA (Alliance for Food Sovereignty in Africa)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://afsafira.org/	Brings together small-scale farmers, pastoralists, fishers, indigenous people, faith communities, consumers, women, and young people from across Africa to create a united and loud voice for food sovereignty.
Ateker Transformation Sustainability Initiatives (ATSI)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://atsi-ug.org/about-us/	Conduct research with farmers where farmers and farmer groups are key players in research process thus using farmer research networks approach. They build capacity of farmers in developing AE related products such as bio-fertilizer and bio-pesticides as inputs. They also carry out advocacy at community level and promote linkages between farmers and researchers.
Bukabooli Community Development initiative	Others	https://www.facebook.com/Bukabooli.community/	Community based natural resource management.
Bulogo Women's Group	Farmers Organization	https://bulogowomensgroup.org/	Promote the need to improve the environment and proper usage of land especially soils for sustainable agriculture. Since the climate mostly determines women livelihoods, BWG works at enhancing environmental protection and management & supports women households to plant trees around their plots of land, home compounds and also construct energy saving stoves.
Climate Action Network	UN Agency	https://climatenetwork.org/	Climate Action Network (CAN) is a global network of more than 1,900 civil society organisations in over 130 countries driving collective and sustainable action to fight the climate crisis and to achieve social justice. CAN convenes and coordinates civil society at the UN climate talks and other international fora.
Community Restoration Initiative Project	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://grassrootsjusticework.org/connect/organization/community-restoration-initiative-project/	They focus on lobbying and advocacy for farmers to transit to agroecology while practicing organic farming.
Eastern and Southern Africa Small scale farmers forum (ESAFF)	Farmers Organization	https://esaffuganda.org/	Enhancement of food security, food sovereignty, and poverty alleviation through regional farmer empowerment through lobbying and advocacy for pro-poor policies.
Eko Veterinary and Agricultural Consultants	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://m.facebook.com/p/Eko-Veterinary-Agricultural-Consultants-LTD-100077495013038/	Distribution of veterinary inputs and Agricultural advisory services.

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
Good Samaritan Support Action	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://vc4a.com/ventures/good-samaritan-support-action/	Contribute towards social-economic empowerment of poor people including orphans and vulnerable children, single women, widows and marginalized women through environmental sustainability through interventions in conservation.
Highlands Organic Company	Others	https://www.ecohubmap.com/company/business/highlands-organic/l0gvj04b	Organic avocado farming, Vegetables and spice production, bee keeping.
Homeland Organics and Agri Tourism	Others	https://homeland-organics-agro-ecological-tourism.business.site/	A training centre that integrates organic agriculture and tourism to promote sustainability.
Jinja Organic Company	Farmer	https://m.facebook.com/p/Jinja-Organic-Company-ltd-100081327102777/	Designed to support local farmers to meet the organic farming standards.
Kasenge Riverford Organic Center	Others	https://www.facebook.com/Kasengeriv/	A training and capacity development center on organic agricultural practices.
Kiwenda Fish Farm	Farmers	https://m.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100068930036082	Practices aquaculture, livestock, poultry, agro forestry, vegetable and cereal farming.
Kulika Uganda	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.kulika.org/	Training farmers on Agroecological practices and principle of school gardens. Promotes indigenous seed and seed banks, market linkages for organic farm produce, value addition to organic produce, strategic networking and partnerships with like-minded organisations.
Ministry of Agriculture, Animal Industry and Fisheries	Governments Department/Agency/Programme	https://www.gou.go.ug/ministry/ministry-agriculture-animal-industry-and-fisheries	The Ministry is the overseer of the agricultural sector where it formulates, reviews and implement national policies, plans, strategies, regulations and standards and enforce laws, regulations and standards along the value chain of crops, livestock and fisheries.
Nakifuma Farmers and Traders Sacco	Farmers Organization	https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/how-rural-farmer-doubled-her-savings-same-budget-using-ash-luwambo?trk=read_related_article-card_title	Farmers make their own fertilizers and pesticides using locally available and sourced resources.
National Association of Professional Environmentalists (NAPE)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://nape.or.ug/	Engages in indigenous seed recovery as well as protection of indigenous seeds, composting and manure, backyard kitchen farming, permaculture,

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
			intercropping, controlling pests using organic ways, use of organic fertilizers from cows, goats chicken etc.
National Organic Agricultural Movement of Uganda (NOGAMU)	Farmers Organization	https://nogamu.org/	A network of organic food producers.
Farmer (Name protected)	Farmer		Uses known agroecological practices and tries out new ones that mostly imitate nature in agriculture.
Rinob Farms	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)		Local chicken production, vegetable production.
Rootical Business Builder	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.rootical.org/	With our startup studio they power East African entrepreneurs to build and own their Agroecological businesses. Purpose driven solutions designed to transform the food system by accelerating farmer transitions to Agroecology and making nutritious, healthy and organic food more affordable and accessible to mainstream consumers.
St. Jude Family Projects	Farmers Organization	https://stjudefamilyprojects.org/	Agricultural and vocational learning center.
SULMA Food Limited	Value Chain Organization (Other than Farmers)	https://www.organic-bio.com/en/company/21353-SULMA-FOODS-LTD	Dehydration, export, packaging and production
Support for Women in Agriculture and Environment (SWAGEN)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://swagenafrika.org/	Supports food security & food sovereignty, and agroecology. Advocates for a transition to agroecology as the food production model in Africa as opposed to industrial agriculture.
Sustainable Agriculture for Rural Development Network (SARD-Net)	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://sard-netuganda.or.ug/	1) Awareness creation on Agroecology for smallholder farmers; 2) Skill youth in Agripreneurship using Agroecology principles; 3) Train smallholder farmers in Climate Resilient Agroecosystem Model (CRAEM); 4) Train smallholder farmers in Community Managed Seed Security Model (CMSSM); 5) Train smallholder farmers in aquaculture and bee keeping; 6) Train smallholder farmers in energy conservation.
Uganda National Young Farmers Association	Farmers Organization	https://unyfa.org/	UNYFA is driven by the desire to have a holistically transformed youth in agriculture for a sustainable economy: its target group is of youth between 12 to 39 years of age who are rural and/or urban agro-based and young farmers in and out of school/ Institutions. Due to diverse interests of farmer groups/farmers'

Organization's Name	Category	Contact Info	Description
			based organizations, young farmers need specific training; UNYFA provides platforms for these youths where they can express and acquire tailor-made training.
UYDNET	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://acsa-ug.org/uydnet/	Provide Black Soldier Fly (BSF) training as well as on community agroecology such as making organic fertilizers, engagement in agroecology enterprises & distribution of indigenous seeds.
Young Farmers Champion	NGO/CSO/FBO	https://www.youngfarminggchampions.com/	The Young Farming Champions (YFC) are identified as youth ambassadors and future influencers working within the agriculture sector.
Young Farmers' Federation of Uganda.	Farmers Organization	https://unyfa.org/about-us/	Capacity building of young farmer members as well as policy advocacy.

4 STAKEHOLDERS CAPACITIES AND NEEDS IN AGROECOLOGY

4.1 STAKEHOLDERS UNDERSTANDING AND APPLICATION OF AGROECOLOGY

Most stakeholders understood the concept of agroecology and their definition of the same fell within the range of the most used terms in defining the concept. Holistic agriculture production systems, sustainability and sustainable systems, environmental friendly and ecosystems featured heavily in the definitions. The bellow word cloud illustrates the mostly used terms in the definition of agroecology by the stakeholders.

FIGURE 4: WORD CLOUD IMPRESSION OF COMMON TERMS USED TO DEFINE AGROECOLOGY

Most stakeholders fully understand a good number of the agroecology elements, with 31 of them fully understanding all the 10 elements, while 95 (74%) of them fully understood 5 or more of the elements. Out of the 129 stakeholders who responded, 10 indicated they fully understood only 1 element, with 10 understanding just one element, and 11 understanding none. The understanding of the elements was

highest amongst the organizations offering support and advisory services and lowest amongst the individual producers and their organizations as well as other value chain actors and their organizations.

FIGURE 5: STAKEHOLDERS UNDERSTANDING OF AGROECOLOGY (AE) ELEMENTS BY NUMBER

Diversity is the most fully understood element of agroecology, with 82% of the stakeholders indicating they fully understood it. Co-creation and sharing of knowledge was fully understood by 74% of the stakeholders, with recycling and resilience being fully understood by 72% and 58% of the stakeholders respectively. Responsible governance and circularity and solidarity economy were the least understood with less than 50% indicating they fully understood either.

FIGURE 6: PERCENTAGE OF STAKEHOLDERS UNDERSTANDING OF EACH AGROECOLOGY ELEMENT

All the stakeholders are already practicing or promoting at least one agroecology principal, with 56% applying or promoting between 3 to 6 principals, and 11% applying or promoting 10 or more. Soil health was the most popular principal with 77% of the stakeholders applying or promoting it. Biodiversity, economic diversification and participation followed in popularity with 71%, 69% and 69% respectively. Connectivity is the least applied and promoted principle with only 47% of the stakeholders indicating they were applying or promoting. There was no clear correlation between the different stakeholders category and the number of agroecology principles they were practicing or promoting.

FIGURE 7: APPLICATION AND PROMOTION OF AGROECOLOGY PRINCIPLES BY STAKEHOLDERS

4.2 CHALLENGES FACED BY THE STAKEHOLDER IN OF AGROECOLOGY TRANSITION

The challenges highlighted by the stakeholders across the 3 countries and the different stakeholders' categories were similar in nature and only differed in the effect across the categories. The most common challenges highlighted were grouped into the following list, prioritized by frequency of mention by the stakeholders:

TABLE 6: CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED BY STAKEHOLDERS IN AGROECOLOGY TRANSITION

Challenge	Effect on Stakeholder category				
	Producers and VC actors	NGOs, CBOs and VCO	Researchers and Academia	INGOs, UN Agencies/ Multilaterals	Private Companies
Inadequate financing/ Financial access	Lack of AE specific financial services Inadequate donor support	Inadequate donor support	Inadequate budgets for AE related research and technology advancement		Inadequate capital and credit facilities for investment/ expansion
Limited technical capacity/ awareness	Limited access to AE information and trainings	Inadequate budget for extension	Inadequate dissemination of research findings	Inadequate extension service provision on AE	Lack of budget for extension on AE
Limited access to appropriate AE technologies	Lack of tailor-made technologies Unaffordable technologies	Lack of information by VC actors on available technologies	Low uptake of technologies by VC actors	Low adoption of technologies by farmers	High cost of AE technologies
Inadequate Specialized EA markets	Market systems not supportive of the AE products Unsegmented markets for AE products	Inability of farmers to meet specialized markets			Unavailability of organic inputs
Lack of synergies among the stakeholders	Uncoordinated programmes and efforts bringing confusion	Lack of coordination leading to inefficiencies	Low coordination between research and extension	Weak structures for stakeholders coordination and consultations	Weak supply chain linkages
Fixed mindset	Resistance to change Fear for the unknown Perception conventional agriculture is more productive	Culture and practice		Inadequate investment in behavior change	Consumer behavior – going for cheap over quality

Challenge	Effect on Stakeholder category					
	Producers and VC actors	NGOs, and VCO	CBOs	Researchers and Academia	INGOs, UN Agencies/ Multilaterals	Private Companies
Climate change and environmental degradation	Unpredictable weather patterns Soil degradation Water scarcity					

Some of the other challenges that features in the responses included low documentation of practices, inadequate advocacy work, inadequate resources mobilization capacity, inadequate project management skills, low levels of producers organizations, limited ICT resources, unattractive prices for AE products, gender inequalities, inadequate leadership and group management skills, limited entrepreneurship skills, land fragmentation, policy and regulatory barriers, research and data gaps, limited access to farmers, and low involvement of youth in AE activities.

FIGURE 8: CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED BY STAKEHOLDERS

4.3 STAKEHOLDERS' CAPACITY BUILDING GAPS

The stakeholders identified several capacity building gaps, which can be classified into three thematic training areas:

a) Organizational related training needs

These were the needs related to strengthening the organization of the value chain actors and strengthening of the organizational and functional capacity of the value chain organizations. The identified training areas under this category were:

- Resources mobilization capacity
- Project management and proposal writing skills
- Gender issues, leadership and group dynamics
- Strategic management and staff retention
- Members mobilization skills
- Good Governance
- Financial and cost management
- Risk management

b) Support related training needs.

These were training needs related to the services that are supportive of agroecology transition. These were mostly identified by NGOs, CSOs, extensionists and other organizations offering support to VC organizations. These were:

- Use of ICT resources and digital farmer training
- Knowledge documentation
- Data collection tools
- Lobbying and Advocacy
- Student training and exchange with Universities both locally and abroad
- Staff training and support, and joint research

c) Agroecology practice and technology needs

These are the needs related to specific agroecology practices and technologies and were mostly flagged by producers and other VC actors. The identified needs were:

- Production of organic pesticides.
- Circular innovations model
- Agroecological market access and value chains
- Organic honey production
- Vermiculture
- PGS and organic certification
- Irrigation
- Tissue culture of bananas and mangoes
- Integrating agroecology farming systems
- Soil fertility management
- Pests and disease management
- Permaculture
- Crop and animal husbandry

The top priority training needs, based on the number of stakeholders:

1. Resources mobilization
2. Integrating agroecology farming systems
3. Pests and disease management
4. Market access of agroecological produce
5. Production of organic pesticides
6. Soil fertility management
7. Crop and animal husbandry
8. Lobbying and advocacy
9. Knowledge documentation
10. Circular innovations model

5 CONCLUSIONS

Stakeholders' involvement is key towards having contextualized agroecology framework and developing the decision tool. Understanding the stakeholders well is important in ensuring the right stakeholders are involved in the co-creation activities. For this involvement to be meaningful, co-creation activities need to be cognizant of the unique characteristics of the stakeholders, capitalizing on their strengths while addressing their needs. Though the understanding of the agroecology elements is fairly good, and application of the principles equally notable, there are still gaps that these stakeholders need support in.

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